

Studies in Copper(II) Chelates: Part I. α, α' -Dipyridyl Mono(biguanide) Copper(II) and o-Phenanthroline Mono(biguanide) Copper(II) Complexes*

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A series of new heterochelates $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})\text{X}_2]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{o-phen})(\text{BigH})\text{X}_2]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{McBigH})\text{X}_2]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{EtBigH})\text{X}_2]$ (where $\text{dipy} = \alpha, \alpha'$ -dipyridyl, $\text{o-phen} = 1, 10$ -phenanthroline, $\text{BigH} = \text{biguanide}$, $\text{McBigH} = \text{Methylbiguanide}$, $\text{EtBigH} = \text{ethylbiguanide}$ and $\text{X} = \text{Cl, Br or I}$) etc. have been synthesized and characterised. The complexes are all highly crystalline, coloured and behave as bi-univalent electrolytes in aqueous solution and also in methanol. Their magnetic moments (≈ 1.80 B.M.) coupled with the absorption spectra in solid state, in water and in methanol, ethanol, DMSO and ethyleneglycol (for the iodide salt) lead to the proposition of distorted octahedral structure. The spectra in aqueous medium give one rather broad, somewhat asymmetric band whereas that in methanol and other solvents for the iodides split into two.

Extensive spectral measurements are also reported on the system $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$: dipyridyl/o-phenanthroline, which indicate the formation of a 1:1 mixed chelate with release of biguanide in solution. Besides, similar measurements are also included for $[\text{Cu}(\text{McBigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2/[\text{Cu}(\text{EtBigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$: o-phenanthroline/ α, α' -dipyridyl again proving 1:1 interaction. Formation Constants for all these mixed chelate systems have been evaluated and these are of the order of 10^8 - 10^9 .

Of the many interesting aspects in the complex chemistry of the $3d^9$ copper (II) ion, one certainly is the large extent of distortion that its complexes suffer due to Jahn Teller effect^{1,2,3}. As a result, most of the copper(II) complexes are either distorted octahedral or distorted tetrahedral. Viewed in this light copper (II) bis(biguanide) ion is one of the very few cases of a near square planar structure, providing an absorption band⁴ around 520 - 530 μ ($\approx 19,000$ cm^{-1}), which is a case for a typical square planar stereochemistry with four nitrogen coordination⁵. A crystal spectra study reveals the expected splittings of the bands, which are not resolved in solution⁶.

Extending our interest in the mixed ligand complexes of transition metals⁷⁻¹⁰ to copper (II), we now report the syntheses of such complexes as $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})\text{X}_2]$,

*A preliminary notice of the studies described in this and several forthcoming papers in the series had appeared earlier. (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 353).

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[Cu(o-phen) (BigH)] X₂ (where dipy = α , α' dipyridyl, o-phen = o-phenanthroline, BigH = biguanide) alongwith studies on their structure. Of the very few heterochelates of copper(II) mention may be made of [Cu(gly) (BigH)] X and [Cu(α -alan) BigH] X (where glyH = glycine, α -alanH = α -alanine and X = Cl⁻, Br⁻ or I⁻)¹¹ as also to a solution study¹² on [Cu(en) (ox)] (en = ethylenediamine and ox = oxalate ion) alongwith several mixed amino acid¹³ chelates.

Two schemes were tried for the syntheses of the mixed chelates. The first involved the addition of α , α' -dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline to the blue monobiguanide copper (II) in aqueous solution. Spectrophotometric studies reported elsewhere⁴ indicate that the formation of the bis(biguanide) copper(II) from aquo copper(II) and biguanide takes place in two steps, the first one being an equilibrium between aquo copper (II) and mono(biguanide) copper(II) upto a pH 4.5-5.0, the second one involving an equilibrium between monobiguanide copper (II) and bis(biguanide) copper (II). We observed that feeding dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline to the solution involving the first equilibrium had disastrous consequences in that the dipyridyl or the o-phenanthroline reacted with the free aquo copper (II) providing sparingly soluble green coloured dichloro (o-phenanthroline) or dichloro (α , α' -dipyridyl) copper (II), the entire equilibrium being shifted. On the contrary, it was quite safe to add the heterocyclic ligands at above pH 5, when a pleasing colour change occurs from light blue to royal blue, indicating the formation of the mixed chelate. The second route involved the formation, *in situ*, of μ -diol bis (α α' -dipyridyl) copper(II) or μ -diol bis(o-phenanthroline) copper(II) at pH 6-7 and reacting these complexes with neutralised biguanide at the same pH.

Both α , α' -dipyridyl mono(biguanide) copper (II) chloride and o-phenanthroline (monobiguanide) copper (II) chloride are obtained as glistening royal blue crystals, which remained unchanged in composition on several recrystallisations from warm water. By double decomposition the corresponding bromide and iodide salts have been obtained. The addition of KI involves much decomposition of the complex; however purification provides fine sky-blue needles of the pure iodide salt. Attempts to obtain salts of other anions provided some information on the range of stability of these mixed chelates. The addition of thiocyanate results in the isolation of pure, intense green diisothiocyanato mono(α , α' -dipyridyl) copper(II)¹⁴ and diisothiocyanato mono(c-phenanthroline) copper (II) as highly insoluble material. Similar reactions occur with excess sodium azide resulting in the precipitation of the insoluble diazido mono (α , α' -dipyridyl/c-phenanthroline) copper (II).

Measurements of conductance in aqueous solution for the chloride and the iodide salt and in methanol for the iodide salt provide values of 240—260 mhos cm² mole⁻¹, indicative of the bi-univalent electrolytic nature of the complexes (cf. table I).

The room temperature magnetic moments of all the complexes are around 1.8 B.M. being close to the spin only value. These values support a planar or a tetragonally distorted octahedral structure rather than a tetrahedral structure which usually derives

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some orbital contribution¹⁵. Besides the positions^{8,16} of the two ligands in the spectrochemical series also opine against such stereochemical view.

TABLE I

Elemental Analysis, Conductances and Magnetic moments

Complex		% Cu	Analysis			Λ_M in aq. soln. (mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹) (t° C)	μ_{eff} . B.M. at 296° abs.
			%N	%Cl/Br/I	%H ₂ O		
1. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] Cl ₂ . 1.5 H ₂ O	Found :	15.20	23.47	16.94	6.20	269 (32°)*	1.82 B.M.
	Reqd. :	15.23	23.47	16.98	6.47		
2. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] Br ₂ . 1.5 H ₂ O	Found :	12.50	19.40	31.52	5.28		
	Reqd. :	12.55	19.35	31.56	5.33		
3. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] I ₂ . H ₂ O	Found :	10.71	16.60	43.00	3.10	266 (32°)	
	Reqd. :	10.74	16.57	42.91	3.04		
4. [Cu (o-Phen) (BigH)] Cl ₂ . 2H ₂ O	Found :	13.91	19.52	15.86	7.96	268 (30°)	1.84
	Reqd. :	14.10	19.43	15.80	8.00		
5. [Cu (o-phen) (BigH)] Br ₂ . H ₂ O	Found :	12.62	19.49	31.10			
	Reqd. :	12.61	19.46	31.07			
6. [Cu (o-phen) (BigH)] I ₂ . H ₂ O	Found :	10.24	15.81	41.29	2.76		
	Reqd. :	10.31	15.92	41.26	2.92		
7. [Cu (dipy) (MeBigH)] Cl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Found :	14.37	22.21	16.11	8.23	253 (31°)	1.81
	Reqd. :	14.42	22.24	16.09	8.17		
8. [Cu (dipy) (MeBigH)] Br ₂ .2H ₂ O	Found :	12.02	18.58	30.12	6.71		
	Reqd. :	12.00	18.50	30.18	6.79		
9. [Cu (dipy) (MeBigH)] I ₂ .0.5H ₂ O	Found :	10.55	16.43	42.62	1.60		
	Reqd. :	10.64	16.39	42.58	1.50		
10. [Cu (dipy) (EtBigH)] Cl ₂ .3H ₂ O	Found :	13.41	20.60	15.10	10.96	242 (31°)	1.84
	Reqd. :	13.45	20.74	15.01	11.43		
11. [Cu (dipy) (EtBigH)] Br ₂ . 2H ₂ O	Found :	11.61	18.13	29.48	7.01		
	Reqd. :	11.69	18.03	29.41	6.62		
12. [Cu (dipy) (EtBigH)] I ₂ . H ₂ O	Found :	10.51	16.26	42.26			
	Reqd. :	10.55	16.29	42.19			
13. [Cu (dipy) Cl ₂]	Found :	21.96	9.71	24.32			
	Calcd. :	21.88	9.64	24.44			
14. [Cu (O-phen) Cl ₂]	Found :	20.16	8.90	22.52			
	Calcd. :	20.20	8.90	22.58			

* Figures in parentheses indicate the temps. at which measurements were made.

μ_{eff} was calculated from the relation $\mu_{eff} = 2.84 (\chi_M(\text{corr.}) \times T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ B.M. where T = 296° abs.

Λ_M (molar conductance) = $2 \times \text{mean } \lambda_{\infty}$, (where $\lambda_{\infty} = \lambda_v(1 + 0.692 \times n_1 \times n_2 \times v^{\frac{1}{2}})$ and n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions.)

'a' means in methanol.

The solution absorption spectra of our complexes provide a broad absorption band around 16,000 cm⁻¹ (cf. fig. I). The frequency of this absorption is certainly at a much higher energy than those in tetrahedral or distorted tetrahedral structures (cf: tetra-

15. J. Lewis and R. A. Walton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, (A), 1559.

16. Reference 2, p. 579.

17. Reference 2, p. 753.

chlorocuprate ion^{18,19}; tetracyanatocuprate²⁰; tetraisothiocyanato copper(II)²¹ and is again somewhat lower than for square planar⁵ stereochemistry. It is therefore, only plausible to invoke a distorted octahedral⁵ structure for the complexes (cf: [Cu (benzimidazole)₄ X₂]⁵ (X=NO₃, NCS etc.). A further support to this is found in the change of the

FIG. 1 Absorption spectra of different complexes.

1. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] Cl₂. 1.5 H₂O, 0.004M in water.
2. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] I₂.H₂O, 0.004 M in water.
3. [Cu (o-phen) (BigH)] Cl₂.2H₂O, 0.004 M in water.
4. [Cu (o-phen) (BigH)] I₂.H₂O, ~0.004 M in water.
5. [Cu (o-phen) (BigH)] I₂. H₂O, 0.002 M in methanol.
6. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] I₂. H₂O, 0.002 M in methanol.
7. [Cu (BigH)₂] Cl₂. 2H₂O, 0.004 M in water.
8. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] Cl₂. 1.5 H₂O, Diffuse Reflectance spectra.
9. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] I₂. H₂O, Diffuse Reflectance spectra.

Optical density scale for (8) and (9) is arbitrary.

spectra for the iodide salt in methanol, ethanol, ethyleneglycol and DMSO compared to the aqueous solution spectra. Compared to these heterochelates the homochelate bis (biguanide) copper (II) with four nitrogen coordination provides a band at still higher energy at 19,000 cm⁻¹ which is what is usually accepted for a square planar configuration. The reflectance spectra of the chloride and the iodide salts (both hydrates) of the mixed

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20. D. Forster and D. M. L. Goodgame, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2796.

21. D. Forster and D. M. L. Goodgame, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 823.

chelate α, α' -dipyridyl monobiguanide copper (II) are also presented along with their solution spectra (cf. fig. 1). The aqueous solution spectra and the diffuse reflectance spectra of the iodide salt show absorption over the same frequency region, which indicates that the iodide salt has the same extent of distortion in the solid, crystalline state as in the aqueous medium. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the chloride salt is substantially different from that in aqueous solution, the aqueous solution spectra again being similar to that of the iodide in aqueous solution. Since the chloride absorbs at a higher frequency in the solid state than when in solution, it is much less distorted in the solid state. The distortion in these two salts probably do not arise out of anion penetration, in which case the spectra of the iodide in solid state should have been very much different from that in aqueous solution. Distortion possibly arises in both cases out of water coordination and that the effect is less vigorous in the chloride than in the iodide.

Further to the simple unsubstituted biguanide, a few alkyl substituted biguanide, namely N^1 -methyl-, N^1 -ethylbiguanides have also been shown to give rise to such mixed complexes. Because of the somewhat lower formation constant values, the pH range offered during such syntheses was narrower and more rigorous setting of conditions was necessary. Whereas mixed chelates could be obtained between α, α' -dipyridyl on the one hand and methyl-/ethyl-biguanide on the other, the corresponding chelates with *o*-phenanthroline could not be isolated.

Magnetic moment values as also the absorption spectra of these complexes also suggest distorted octahedral configuration, as in the case of the unsubstituted biguanide. Typical solution spectra of selected complexes and the spectral properties, magnetic moments and the conductances appear in fig. 1 and in table I and II.

We have also carried out extensive spectrophotometric measurements in aqueous solution on the absorption spectral changes of bis-(biguanide) copper (II) chloride consequent on the addition of α, α' -dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline (cf. Fig. II). The red-violet colour of the original complex changed to blue-violet on adding the heterocyclic bases. Detailed spectral measurements indicate a 1 : 1 interaction between the complex and the heterocyclic base, as determined by a molar ratio variation (cf. Fig. IV). The λ_{max} . of 530 $m\mu$ of aqueous bis (biguanide) copper (II) chloride gets modified to 550—580 $m\mu$ and the spectral data remains unmodified after the addition of α, α' -dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline in excess of one mole proportion. This 1 : 1 interaction, pointed as it were to any of the following three probable reactions:

and the necessity therefore arose to decide on the exact course of the reaction. That the reaction did not run as in (i) was adequately proved by running the spectra of 1 mole copper (II) chloride and one of dipyridyl at the same pH , which provides an absorption curve significantly different from the one we had in this study (compare curves 2 and 12 as also curves 9 and 11 in Fig. II). Proving that the real course of the reaction was (ii) would also disprove (iii) and we therefore decided to verify the release of free biguanide in solution. Although testing for biguanide by the addition of ammoniacal copper (II) sulfate is a well-known procedure, this course would also decompose the

TABLE II
Spectral Data of Mixed Chelates

Complex.	State	Colour	Absorption Spectral	ϵ
			Bands Cm^{-1}	
1. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] Cl_2	Aq. solution	Royal blue	16950-15630	63.50
	Solid	Royal blue	17860-17240	—
2. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] I_2	Aq. Solution	Deep blue	16660-15630	66.00
	Solid	Sky—blue	16390-15630	—
	Methanol Solution	Light green	(i)23810-22730	(i)203
		with yellow tinge.	(ii)13510-12820	(ii)140
	Ethanol Solution	Straw yellow	(i)23260-22730	(i) *
			(ii)13510-12660	(ii)149
	Ethylene glycol	Green	(i)24390-23260	(i)122.5
DMSO	Green	(ii)13890-13160	(ii) 99.0	
		(i)28570-	(i)493	
		(ii)15870-14490	(ii) 71.25	
3. [Cu (BigH) $_2$] Cl_2	Aq. Solution	Rose-Red	19230-18870	41.25**
4. [Cu (o-phen) (BigH)] Cl_2	Aq. Solution	Deep blue	16950-15630	55.50
5. [Cu (O-phen) (BigH)] I_2	Aq. Solution	Deep blue	16950-15630	*
	DMSO	Green	(i)28570-	(i)485
			(ii)15380-13890	(ii) 75
Methanol Solution	Yellowish Green.	(i)22730-22220	(i) 242.0	
		(ii)13330-12820	(ii) 150	
6. [Cu (dipy) (MeBigH)] Cl_2	Aq. Solution	Royal blue	16400-15630	68.00
7. [Cu (dipy) (MeBigH)] I_2	Aq. Solution	Deep blue	16400-15380	*
	Methanol Solution	Greenish yellow	(i)22730	(i) *
			(ii)13510-12820	(ii) *
8. [Cu (dipy) (EtBigH)] Cl_2	Aq. Solution	Royal blue	16660-15380	67.50
9. [Cu (dipy) (EtBigH)] I_2	Aq. Solution	Deep blue	16950-15380	*
	Methanol Solution	Greenish yellow	(i)23260	(i) *
			(ii)13510-12820	(ii) *
10. [Cu (dipy) (BigH)] Cl_2	[Cu (BigH) $_2$] Cl_2 in aq. soln. and dipyrityl in 1:1 ratio at pH 7.	Royal blue.	16950-15880	63.75
11. [Cu (dipy) (MeBigH)] Cl_2	[Cu (MeBigH) $_2$] Cl_2 in aq. soln. and dipyrityl in 1:1 ratio at pH 7.	Royal blue.	16660-15380	69.00
12. [Cu (dipy) (EtBigH)] Cl_2	[Cu (EtBigH) $_2$] Cl_2 in aq. soln. and dipyrityl in 1:1 ratio at pH 7.	Royal blue.	16660-15380	68.50
13. [Cu (o-phen) (BigH)] Cl_2	[Cu (BigH) $_2$] Cl_2 in aq. soln. and o-phenanthroline in 1:1 ratio at pH 7.	Deep blue	16950-15880	56.25
14. [Cu (o-phen) (MeBigH)] Cl_2	[Cu (MeBigH) $_2$] Cl_2 in aq. soln. and o-phenanthroline in 1:1 ratio at pH 7.	Deep blue	16400-15380	59.25
15. [Cu (o-phen) (EtBigH)] Cl_2	[Cu (EtBigH) $_2$] Cl_2 in aq. soln. and o-phenanthroline in 1:1 ratio at pH 7.	Deep blue	16400-15380	52.5

* Optical density measurements were made in saturated solutions. Due to some uncertainty, the molar extinction coeffs. are not presented in the Table II.

** Extinction co-eff. value reported by Ray and Rây⁴ is 38.5 (at 19230 Cm^{-1}).

DMSO = Dimethylsulfoxide.

mixed complex. In a typical test run 0.008M $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex was treated with 0.008 M α, α' -dipyridyl, thus expectedly releasing 0.008M free biguanide in solution according to (ii). We forced this excess biguanide to combine with 0.004M $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to provide 0.004M $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2$ in solution and then ran the spectra again at pH 9.0. This spectra was compared with the spectra of 0.008M copper (II) bis-(biguanide) chloride, 0.008M α, α' -dipyridyl and 0.004 M copper (II) bis (biguanide) chloride at pH 9.0. The two spectral curves revealed very satisfactory concurrence (compare curves 3 and 4 in fig. II). Fig. II presents a large number of spectra depicting the formation of the dipyridyl-biguanide mixed complex at several pH. For comparison, we include several spectra of the copper (II)—dipyridyl system in 1 : 1 ratio at several pH. A study of these curves amply justify the formation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})]^{2+}$ complex in solution around pH 6—pH 7. A typical spectra of the isolated complex is also included for comparison. That free biguanide was being released in solution as a result of mixed chelate formation was also strongly indicated by the substantial increase in pH of the resulting solution: thus 0.008 M aqueous bis(biguanide) copper (II) chloride dihydrate gives a pH 7.2 whereas that due to addition of 0.008 M α, α' -dipyridyl provides a pH of 8.95. Indeed this knowledge was essential in order to arrive at comparable spectra in the above case. Addition of copper(II) chloride dihydrate which is distinctly acidic lowers the pH to around 7.0 and unless the pH is raised to around 9.0, the two spectra are substantially different. Furthermore, the effect of pH was verified by adjusting the pH of the solution of 0.008M $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008M dipyridyl from around 9.0 to 7.0, when it was found that the spectra of the mixed chelate formed in solution was perfectly superimposable on the spectra of 0.008M $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ obtained earlier through direct syntheses (compare curves 1 and 2 in fig. II).

For brevity only a few curves are given on the solution spectral studies, taking $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} : \alpha, \alpha'$ -dipyridyl system as a typical case. Similar spectral studies were undertaken for $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} : o$ -phenanthroline system as well. Besides, the systems : bis(methylbiguanide) copper (II) chloride/bis(ethylbiguanide) copper (II) chloride and α, α' -dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline were also extensively investigated. These latter studies involving *o*-phenanthroline were considered obligatory because of our failure to isolate the mixed chelates in crystalline state with sufficient purity. The results indicate a 1 : 1 mixed chelate formation between substituted biguanides and the heterocyclic bases as revealed by molar ratio variation method (cf. fig. IV and fig. V). That the optical density values do not level off after the addition of one mole α, α' -dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline, although reveal a definite break in the curve, probably indicates some slight further interaction.

The pH variation study of different mixed chelate systems are graphically represented in fig. III. This shows that with the substituted biguanides the pH region over which the mixed chelates attain maximum formation is narrower than that with the simple unsubstituted biguanide. These curves have been utilised in the evaluation of the formation constant of the mixed chelates. A reasonable assumption is made that at or around pH 4.5, the copper(II) ion is present either as $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})]^{2+}$ or as the mixed chelate, with negligible amount of copper mono(biguanide). Around this pH region the formation of $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})]^{2+}$ is complete as shown by a recent study²² and the assumption that no appreciable copper (II) mono(biguanide) exists in solution is supported by the fact that lowering the pH

FIG. II. Solutions spectral studies on the system $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; α, α' -Dipyridyl.

1. $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M aqueous solution.
2. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M + α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.008 M, at pH 7.2. ✓
3. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M + α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.008 M + $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.004 M at pH 8.95.
4. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M + α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.008 M + $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.004 M at pH 8.95.
5. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M + α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.004 M at pH 9.4.
6. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M + α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.006 M at pH 9.4.
7. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M + α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.008 M at pH 9.4.
8. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M + α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.014 M at pH 9.4.
9. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M + α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.008 M at pH 5.
10. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M at pH 5.
11. $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M + α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.008 M at pH 5.
12. $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M + α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.008 M at pH 7.

provides $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_2]^0$ as evidenced through isolation of the complex. Release of biguanide from $[\text{Cu}(\text{dipy})(\text{BigH})]^{2+}$ at lower pH is only to be expected because of protonation of uncoordinated =NH groups, which is less probable with a coordinated dipyridyl. Formation constant evaluation at several pH provides reasonably constant values, which is a test of the validity of our assumptions. The optical density values were therefore analysed to determine the concentration of the mixed chelate and the copper (II) mono(dipyridyl) complex. Thus, optical density (D) = $\epsilon_A C_A + \epsilon_B C_B$, where C_A and C_B are the respective concentrations of the two species and ϵ_A and ϵ_B are their respective molar extinction coefficients. The molar extinction coefficients were obtained from a pH variation study of the respective systems. The total of C_A and C_B was the starting concentration of the copper (II) bis (biguanide) complex. The formation constant of the dipyridyl—biguanide mixed

chelate was given by:

The concentration of [BigH] was obtained from a knowledge of the working pH and the two dissociation constants of the biguanide as follows:

$$\text{Total uncomplexed biguanide} = \text{[BigH]} + \frac{\text{[BigH]} \text{[H}^+]}{K_{a1}} + \frac{\text{[BigH]} \text{[H}^+]^2}{K_{a1} \cdot K_{a2}}$$

$$\text{where } K_{a1} = \frac{\text{[BigH]} \text{[H}^+]}{\text{[BigH}_2^+]} \text{ and } K_{a2} = \frac{\text{[BigH}_2^+ \text{]} \text{[H}^+]}{\text{[BigH}_3^{2+}]}$$

Such calculations provided the values of the formation constants of the mixed chelates as given in table III. The formation constants of all the copper(II) mixed chelates arising out

FIG. III. pH variation studies of bis-biguanide copper (II) chloride (or bis-subst. biguanide copper(II) chloride) and α, α' -dipyridyl (or o-phenanthroline).

1. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M and α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.008 M.
 2. $[\text{Cu}(\text{MeBigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M and α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.008 M.
 3. $[\text{Cu}(\text{MeBigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M and o-phenanthroline, 0.008 M.
 4. $[\text{Cu}(\text{EtBigH})_2] \text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M and o-phenanthroline, 0.008 M.
- Inset Curve* : $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M and α, α' -dipyridyl, 0.008 M.

of the combination of biguanide or substituted biguanides on the one hand and α, α' -dipyridyl/o-phenanthroline on the other have been evaluated from similar spectrophotometric

FIG. IV. Solution composition studies on mixed complex formation; molar ratio variation of α, α' -dipyridyl against $[\text{Cu}(\text{BIGH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.008 M aqueous solution.

1. At 620 $\text{m}\mu$ and at pH 7.2
2. At 570 $\text{m}\mu$ and at pH 9.4.
3. At 700 $\text{m}\mu$ and at pH 7.2
4. At 620 $\text{m}\mu$ and at pH 9.4
5. At 690 $\text{m}\mu$ and at pH 9.4 .

FIG. V. Solution composition studies on mixed complex formation, molar ratio variation of o-phenanthroline against bis-(substituted) biguanide copper (II) chlorides, 0.008 M aqueous solution.

1. $[\text{Cu}(\text{EtBigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and o-phenanthroline at 620 $\text{m}\mu$ and at pH 7.
2. $[\text{Cu}(\text{MeBigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and o-phenanthroline at 710 $\text{m}\mu$ and at pH 7.
3. Same as in (1), at 710 $\text{m}\mu$.

TABLE III

Formation Constant Values of the Heterochelate Complexes

Initial concn. of bis (biguanide) (or subst. bis (biguanide) complexes)=0.008M

Initial concn. of α , α' -dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline=0.008 MWavelength of measurements=620 m μ

ϵ [Cu(dipy) (BigH) Cl ₂	=63.75	ϵ [Cu (o-phen) (BigH)] Cl ₂	=56.25
ϵ [Cu(dipy) (MeBigH)] Cl ₂	=69.00	ϵ [Cu (o-phen) (MeBigH)] Cl ₂	=59.25
ϵ [Cu(dipy)(EtBigH)] Cl ₂	=68.50	ϵ [Cu (o-phen) (EtBigH)] Cl ₂	=52.50
ϵ [Cu(dipy)] ²⁺	=21.30	ϵ [Cu(o-phen)] ²⁺	=17.20

System	pH of measurements	O.D. (1 Cm cell)	Concn. of [Cu (dipy)] ²⁺ or [Cu (o-phen)] ²⁺	[Mixed Complex]	[BigH] or [Subst. BigH]	K
1. [Cu (BigH) ₂] Cl ₂ and α , α' -dipyridyl.	4.5 5.0	0.390 0.455	0.002827M 0.001296	0.005173M 0.006704	1.083 \times 10 ⁻⁹ 2.794 \times 10 ⁻⁹	1.69 \times 10 ⁹ 1.85 \times 10 ⁹
2. [Cu (Me BigH) ₂] Cl ₂ and α , α' -dipyridyl	4.5 5.0	0.236 0.345	0.006625 0.004340	0.001375 0.003660	1.631 \times 10 ⁻⁹ 4.487 \times 10 ⁻⁹	1.27 \times 10 ⁸ 1.88 \times 10 ⁹
3. [Cu (EtBigH) ₂] Cl ₂ and α , α' -dipyridyl	5.0 5.5	0.310 0.438	0.005043 0.002331	0.002957 0.005669	4.369 \times 10 ⁻⁹ 1.104 \times 10 ⁻⁸	1.34 \times 10 ⁸ 2.20 \times 10 ⁸
4. [Cu (BigH) ₂] Cl ₂ and o-phenanthroline	4.5 5.0	0.362 0.450	0.002382 0.001280	0.005618 0.006720	1.038 \times 10 ⁻⁹ 2.789 \times 10 ⁻⁹	2.27 \times 10 ⁹ 1.88 \times 10 ⁹
5. [Cu (MeBigH) ₂] Cl ₂ and o-phenanthroline	4.5 5.0	0.200 0.294	0.006518 0.004282	0.001482 0.003718	1.620 \times 10 ⁻⁹ 4.466 \times 10 ⁻⁹	1.40 \times 10 ⁸ 1.94 \times 10 ⁸
6. [Cu (EtBigH) ₂] Cl ₂ and o-phenanthroline	5.0 5.5	0.248 0.324	0.004872 0.002719	0.003128 0.005281	4.313 \times 10 ⁻⁹ 1.146 \times 10 ⁻⁸	1.49 \times 10 ⁸ 1.69 \times 10 ⁸

measurements. The molar extinction co-efficients of the chelates [Cu(dipy)]²⁺ and [Cu(o-phen)]²⁺ were determined from a pH variation and spectrophotometric measurements on the system CuCl₂. 2H₂O: α , α' -dipyridyl/o-phenanthroline. While doing so a pH region of 4.5—5.5 was determined to be the range over which the mono-complexes showed reasonable constancy of optical density. Beyond this range there was a distinct, rapid increase in the optical density values because of the formation of μ -diol complexes (compare inset curve in fig. III). Because of these optical changes depending on pH of the system, we thought this pH range 4.5—5.5 to be the most suitable region over which we could undertake with sufficient dependence the calculation of the formation constants of the mixed chelates. During all these solution studies no attempt was made to maintain ionic strength constant by the addition of an electrolyte such as KCl, KNO₃ or NaClO₄ because of tricky solubility relations of the mixed chelate.

The evaluated formation constants provide a value of the order of 10⁸—10⁹, which values compare favourably with a series of copper (II) mixed chelates containing α , α' -dipyridyl on the one hand and salicylic acid, sulfosalicylic acid etc. on the other.²²

EXPERIMENTAL

Biguanide acid sulfate and substituted (methyl- and ethyl-) biguanide acid sulfates were synthesized by following published procedures^{23,24} and were recrystallised from hot water.

The complexes described in this paper are in general soluble in water, DMSO and ethyleneglycol and insoluble in alcohol and methanol except the iodide complexes which are moderately soluble. Unless otherwise mentioned the complexes were all dried in air.

(1) α, α' -Dipyridyl-Biguanide Copper (II) Chloride: Biguanide acid sulfate (0.9 g) was dissolved in hot water (10-15 ml.) and treated with an aqueous solution of barium chloride (1.15 g in 5 ml.). The mixture was digested on the steam bath for 30 mins., filtered and the filtrate treated with copper (II) chloride solution (0.8 g in 5 ml water). The pH of the solution was raised to 6 by dilute NH_4OH , when a blue solution formed. This blue solution was treated with a rectified spirit solution of α, α' -dipyridyl (0.6 g in 5 ml). An intense royal blue solution resulted and brilliant royal blue crystals started separating, after allowing to stand for an hour, the crystals were filtered and were recrystallised from a small volume of hot water.

(2) α, α' Dipyridyl- Biguanide Copper (II) Bromide : This was obtained by meta-thetic reaction using the above chloride salt and KBr and was recrystallised from warm water.

(3) α, α' -Dipyridyl-Biguanide Copper (II) Iodide : The above chloride salt was dissolved in warm water and cooled. To this solution, a dilute solution of KI (a few ml.) was added dropwise with stirring. First a dirty green precipitate appears followed by a light blue one on the addition of a few drops more of KI solution. The precipitate was cooled in ice, filtered and treated with hot water on a steam bath. A dirty brown precipitate remains undissolved. At this stage, the solution was filtered and the clear blue solution allowed to crystallise. Fine needles of dark sky-blue colour separated.

The corresponding o-phenanthroline—biguanide copper (II) complexes were all prepared by following procedures similar to those of the above α, α' -dipyridyl complexes.

(4) α, α' -Dipyridyl-Methylbiguanide Copper (II) Chloride: Methylbiguanide acid sulfate (0.96 g) was dissolved in hot water (10 ml) and treated with an aqueous solution of barium chloride dihydrate (1.3 g in 5 ml.). The mixture was digested on steam bath for 30 mins., filtered and the filtrate treated with copper (II) chloride solution (0.34 g in 5 ml. water). Now the pH of the solution was raised to 7-7.5 dilute NH_4OH . A red-violet solution formed. This red-violet solution was treated with an alcoholic solution of α, α' -dipyridyl (0.3 g in 3-5 ml.) with constant stirring to give a deep blue solution. Now the pH of the solution was lowered to 6.5 with the help of dil. (2N) HCl. Immediate copious deep blue precipitate with violet tinge was formed. On allowing to stand for 30 mins. at room temp and finally cooling in ice, the crystals were filtered. These were recrystallised from small volume of warm water and filtered.

23. D. Karipides and W. C. Fernelius, *Inorganic Syntheses*, 1963, 7, 56.

24. F. Emich, *Monatsch*, 1883, 4, 394.

The bromide and iodide salts of α, α' -dipyridyl—methyl-biguanide copper (II) complexes were prepared like the corresponding bromide and iodide salts of α, α' -dipyridyl-biguanide copper (II) complexes. Similar procedures were followed for the α, α' -dipyridyl-ethylbiguanide complexes.

(5) *Dichloro-(α, α' -Dipyridyl/o-phenanthroline) Copper (II)*: α, α' -Dipyridyl/o-phenanthroline—biguanide copper (II) chloride prepared as described above was dissolved in water and the pH of the solution was lowered to 4—4.5 when bright green crystalline precipitate formed slowly. After 2—4 hrs, the crystals were filtered, washed with cold water and alcohol and dried in air.

Bis(biguanide) or [bis(substituted) biguanide] copper (II) chlorides were synthesized by following published procedures^{24, 25}. Their purity was checked by analysis.

Analytical Methods: Water of hydration was determined by loss at 110–115° for one hour.

Copper was first precipitated as CuS with H₂S. This precipitate was then dissolved in nitric acid-sulfuric acid mixture and was estimated iodometrically.

Nitrogen was estimated by combustion technique (Dumas' method).

Halogens were estimated as silver halides as usual.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the complexes at room temp. were made by a Gouy Balance with field strength 8.366×10^3 gauss, using G. R. grade copper (II) sulfate pentahydrate as a standard. Diamagnetic corrections were taken from Selwood²⁶.

The spectra of the isolated complexes were run in aqueous or methanolic medium at 0.008 *M* or 0.004 *M* concentration in a Hilger and Watts UVISPEK Spectrophotometer using 1 cm cells.

Solution spectral studies on the composition and formation pH range were run at 0.008 *M* bis(biguanide) and [bis(substituted) biguanide] copper(II) chloride level. The weighed complex was dissolved in about 15 ml. water, then weighed amount of dipyridyl or o-phenanthroline dissolved in little spirit (2-3 ml) was added, pH adjusted to the desired value using a Beckman Zeromatic pH meter and finally volume made up to 25 ml with water. The spectra were run over the range 400 m μ —750 m μ . pH variations were made with 0.008 *M* copper (II) bis(biguanide) or [bis(substituted) biguanide] chloride, 0.008 *M* α, α' -dipyridyl/o-phenanthroline within the range pH 4.5—pH 9.0. Molar ratio variations were done at constant (0.008 *M*) copper (II) bis(biguanide) and [bis(substituted) biguanide] chloride, varying dipyridyl/o-phenanthroline (0.002 *M*—0.014 *M*) at a fixed pH 7.

25. P. Ráy and P. N. Bagchi, *This Journal*, 1939, **16**, 617.

26. P. W. Selwood, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1956, p. 78.

Conductivities in water or methanol were measured by Philips conductivity bridge type PR 9500.

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